

PROXEMIC BEHAVIOR IN A MULTI- USER VIRTUAL REALITY EXPERIENCE FOR MULTILINGUAL CULTURAL HERITAGE EDUCATION

Erica Rocchi¹, Daniela Zini¹, Melissa Lamonaca¹ and Marco Carli^{1,2}

¹Università degli Studi Roma Tre, ²Consorzio Nazionale Interuniversitario per le telecomunicazioni
(CNIT)

SOCIAL XR FOR CULTURAL HERITAGE AND LEARNING

Virtual Reality (VR) is increasingly being used in the fields of **education** and **cultural heritage**, while **Social Extended Reality (XR)** enables **shared** and **immersive experiences** among users.

PROXEMIC BEHAVIOR ANALYSIS

Based on Hall's theoretical model^[1], five spatial zones can be identified: **intimate** (<0.45m), **personal** (0.45m-1.2m), **social** (1.2m-3.6m), **public-close** (3.6m-7.6m), and **public-far** (>7.6m).

[1] E. T. Hall. The Hidden Dimension: man's use of space in public and in private. Anchor Books, 1969.

OBJECTIVE

Two main goals:

RQ1: To explore **how users behave spatially** when interacting in a shared VR environment.

RQ2: To evaluate whether such an application could serve as an **effective learning tool** in a **multilingual cultural heritage context**.

VR APPLICATION

Application: developed in **Unity (v.2022.3)** with Netcode for GameObjects (NGO), Relay, Lobby e Vivox.

Devices: Meta Quest 3, connected via a 5G WiFi 7 router with a 5G SIM card.

A guide (with the crown) explaining the site to a user.

Frontal view of the presbytery.

METHODOLOGY

- **Languages:** Italian (12), Spanish (12), French (11), English (11), Portuguese (6).
- **Structure:** 15-min lesson on *Santa Maria Antiqua*, then exploration task.
- **Evaluation:** SSQ^[2], SUS^[3], social presence^[4], and comprehension questionnaires.
- **Data:** Headset and controller positions recorded throughout.

Meta Quest 3

TP-Link Deco BE65

[2] R. S. Kennedy et al. "Simulator sickness questionnaire: An enhanced method for quantifying simulator sickness". In: The international journal of aviation psychology 3.3 (1993).

[3] J. Brooke. "SUS-A quick and dirty usability scale". In: Usability evaluation in industry 189.194 (1996), pp. 4-7.

[4] M. Orduna et al. "Methodology to Assess Quality, Presence, Empathy, Attitude, and Attention in 360-degree Videos for Immersive Communications". In: IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing (2023).

EXPERIMENTS

- **Participants (N = 52, age 18–64)** – 48% teachers.
- **Groups (N = 20):**
 - 8 groups of 2.
 - 12 groups of 3.
- **Language comprehension:**
 - 20 did **not** understand the guide's language.
 - 32 **did** understand it.
- **VR experience:**
 - 51.9% **first-time users**.
 - 48.1% **used VR before**.

A group of experimenters during the virtual visit.

RESULTS – CYBERSICKNESS AND USABILITY

Cybersickness (SSQ)	Usability (SUS)
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• SSQ weighting:<ul style="list-style-type: none">• 38.91 ± 35.22 → corresponds to mild/negligible symptoms.• Subscale analysis: Disorientation showed the highest scores.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• SUS Score:<ul style="list-style-type: none">• 70.99 → corresponds to the 41st–59th percentile compared to systems evaluated with SUS over time.• Good, but could improve.

RESULTS – SOCIAL PRESENCE

RESULTS – LEARNING

Participants' understanding was **slightly above sufficiency**, with **no significant effect of language**.

- **One-way ANOVA:** $F = 0.67$, $p = 0.615$ → *no significant differences*.
- **t-test (language proficiency):** $t = 0.89$, $p = 0.38$ → *no effect of comprehension language*.

RESULTS - PROXEMICS

Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) of inter-user distance between the users, aggregated across all sessions and all users.

RESULTS - PROXEMICS

Marked behavioral shift from near to far distances:

- **Intimate & personal zones:** less used, more distinct.
- **Distant zones:** broader and less differentiated.

Dunn's post-hoc test (Holm correction): pairwise comparisons between proxemic zones.

Heatmap:

- *Lighter cells* → stronger evidence of difference (low p-values).
- *Darker cells* → no significant difference.

RESULTS – 2/3 GROUPS

Group size affects only close interpersonal distances – not usability, presence, or performance.

Social Distance (Mann–Whitney + Bonferroni):

- **Intimate zone:** *Significant difference* ($U = 436.0$, $p = 0.0008$, **large effect**).
- **Personal zone:** *Significant difference* ($U = 418.0$, $p = 0.0095$, **medium effect**).
- **Other zones:** *No significant differences*.

CONCLUSIONS

Users mostly stayed within the **social zone**, mirroring real-world interactions.

System usability could be improved overall, **social presence** remained high.

Comprehension adequate across all languages → likely thanks to **visual & interactive** VR content.

Group size affects only close interpersonal distances → users tends to stand **closer** when group size is larger.

LESSON LEARNED AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Lesson learned:

- **Spatial monitoring** helps design user comfort and behavior
- **Model weight matters:** high-fidelity reconstructions impact performance, especially on standalone 5G devices
- **Multi-metric approach:** quality of experience must be integrated and tuned to users' expectations.

Future directions:

- Broaden scenarios **beyond digital heritage.**
- Compare **VR vs traditional lessons.**
- Examine **avatar realism** and its effect on learning.

THANK YOU FOR THE ATTENTION!
Questions?

*All icons used in this presentation are from Flaticon (www.flaticon.com).